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The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Enhancing the Intellectual Potential of Organizations

KEYWORDS

corporate social responsibility,
social policy,
intellectual potential,
innovative capital,
human capital,
multi-criteria evaluation,
personnel management,
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ABSTRACT

Introduction. In the context of economic globalization, enterprises face the need to enhance their innovative potential, which serves as the foundation for ensuring long-term competitiveness. One of the factors influencing these processes is corporate social policy, which acts as a tool for shaping the intellectual potential of organizations. Social initiatives implemented within the framework of corporate policy can significantly impact innovation activity and the development of a company's scientific potential.

The study is aimed at investigating the relationship between corporate social policy and the level of intellectual potential in enterprises.

Materials and methods. In order to address this task, a comprehensive approach was employed, incorporating theoretical and empirical analysis. The theoretical foundation of the study is based on a review of publications in the fields of corporate social responsibility and innovation activity. Empirical analysis was conducted using multi-criteria evaluation methods, including the analytic hierarchy process. Data from seven machine-building enterprises were collected, enabling a comparative analysis, identification of key trends, and calculation of intellectual potential indices for each enterprise.

Results. The study identified criteria reflecting the level of intellectual potential in enterprises, such as staff qualifications, access to training, implementation of innovative technologies, the number of scientific developments, and employee social support. The obtained data revealed disparities in the level of intellectual resource development, highlighting the importance of corporate social policy in shaping these resources. Using the analytic hierarchy process, final intellectual potential indices were calculated for all enterprises, allowing for the identification of organizations that most effectively leverage social policy.

Conclusion. The research results confirm the importance of a comprehensive approach to corporate social policy for enhancing the intellectual potential of enterprises. The findings can be used to develop recommendations for improving social policy in machine-building enterprises to increase their competitiveness and innovation activity.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of studying corporate social policy in the context of shaping the intellectual potential of enterprises is driven by rapid changes in the economic and social environment, as well as the growing role of human capital as a factor of competitiveness. Companies face the need to implement innovative solutions, which requires not only technological changes but also the optimization of internal processes aimed at developing intellectual resources. In this regard, corporate social policy, focused on creating favorable conditions for professional growth and employee development, acquires strategic importance for enterprises seeking to enhance their innovative potential.

The relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and innovation continues to attract the attention of the scientific community. Research confirms that CSR can significantly influence the development of an organization's innovative potential. In particular, it has been established that CSR enhances the positive impact on research and development outcomes, which is especially evident when analyzing the number of patents obtained by companies. At the same time, excessive focus on social aspects may lead to resource misallocation, negatively affecting firms' market value. The collected data require further examination in the context of resource optimization at all stages of the innovation process [1].

Personnel management and the implementation of social technologies also play a role in shaping and developing the intellectual potential of enterprises. Approaches to applying social technologies in human resource management are aimed at improving the efficiency of innovation processes. This approach includes the use of information technologies to develop and strengthen intellectual capital. Supporting this theory are research findings emphasizing how the effective use of knowledge at all management levels contributes to increased productivity and the implementation of innovations within companies [2; 3].

The commercialization of scientific research is an integral element of cultivating personnel oriented toward innovation in the knowledge economy. Amid intensifying competition, enhancing competitiveness through the commercialization of innovations acquires strategic importance. The ability to transform scientific results into practical applications forms the basis for training highly qualified specialists. Thus, commercialization serves as a factor in increasing competitiveness and a significant component of sustainable innovative development in knowledge-driven

economies, where the critical element is the integration of research potential into production processes [4; 5].

In recent years, environmental innovations and their connection with CSR have become the subject of intensive scientific research. According to a number of authors, the impact of CSR on companies' environmental performance is not direct. Instead, CSR contributes to the improvement of environmental strategy and stimulates the development of innovations aimed at resource efficiency, which in turn enhances production performance. These conclusions are supported by a number of empirical studies demonstrating the link between CSR strategies and enterprises' resource efficiency [6]. Similar results are also observed in the context of corporate governance, where CSR contributes to improved resource (including environmental) indicators, as well as the adoption of innovations aimed at enhancing the quality of intellectual capital and transforming management strategies in line with the principles of sustainable development and social responsibility [7].

Institutional and strategic factors determining the choice of CSR strategy are equally important. In this context, strategic approaches to CSR often focus on social factors and institutional pressures arising from regulatory and legal changes. Such external and internal factors influence innovation processes, which is particularly evident in environments with limited institutional development, characteristic of emerging economies where inadequate social infrastructure and legal mechanisms can hinder innovation adoption [8; 9].

The socioeconomic aspects and their role in shaping innovative potential also require special attention. Modern information technologies play a crucial role in personnel management and production process optimization, enhancing productivity and fostering organizational innovation. In this regard, information technologies serve both as a resource and a mechanism for implementing corporate innovation strategies, enabling multi-channel knowledge integration and workforce optimization to achieve high economic and innovation performance [10]. Improving production efficiency through project management is considered a key component of the innovation process, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises, where the speed of implementing changes determines their ability to gain competitive advantages [11].

The impact of foreign economic activity on organizational innovation development is examined through the lens of its connection to global economic processes [12]. At the same time, intellectual capital is recognized as a critical component of economic

security strategies for both enterprises and the state, particularly in the context of strategic management and the global challenges of digital transformation [13]. Additionally, tax incentives for innovation investments are viewed as a prerequisite for developing the real sector of the economy, highlighting the need to improve fiscal and financial mechanisms in the context of driving innovative change [14].

Theoretical models exploring the impact of CSR on innovation processes represent a significant direction in business research. One such approach is a model emphasizing the relationship between social responsibility and corporate financial performance [15]. This model helps clarify how CSR stimulates innovation and financial growth in organizations, identifying mechanisms through which corporate strategies enhance long-term value and competitiveness. Similarly, research on entrepreneurial characteristics and organizational management reveals how these factors influence successful innovation implementation in small enterprises, where adaptability and creativity serve as key drivers of change [16]. Furthermore, the model confirms the importance of social responsibility and resource efficiency in innovation processes, where the integration of innovations fosters economic growth and sustainable development [17].

The study is aimed at analyzing the role of corporate social policy in shaping the intellectual potential of enterprises and identifying factors contributing to its development. In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks must be addressed:

1. Assess the impact of corporate social policy on the development of the intellectual potential of the company's employees.
2. Examine the relationship between CSR and innovation activity of the organization.
3. Analyze the role of social technologies in the formation of intellectual capital within enterprises.

The significance of the study lies in the practical applicability of its findings for optimizing corporate social policy strategies aimed at improving the management of intellectual resources.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research materials included articles published in peer-reviewed journals such as Journal of Management Studies, Emerging Markets Finance and Trade, The Journal of Technology Transfer, Journal of Business Ethics, Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting, Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Quality and Quantity, and others.

In order to analyze the role of corporate social policy in shaping the intellectual potential of enterprises, a multi-criteria evaluation method using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was employed. This method allows for a quantitative assessment of the influence of various social policy-related factors on the intellectual capital of organizations. The study utilized data from seven machine-building enterprises characterized by varying degrees of CSR implementation and intellectual resource development.

1. Criteria significance assessment

The first stage involved identifying criteria that reflect an enterprise's intellectual potential. These criteria include:

- Employee qualification level;
- Access to training and professional development;
- Degree of innovative technology adoption;
- Number of scientific developments and patents;
- Effectiveness of employee social support (for example, benefits, bonuses, in-house social infrastructure).

In order to evaluate the significance of each criterion, the pairwise comparison method was used, which determined the weight of each criterion relative to others. The weight coefficients (w_i) for each criterion were calculated using the following equation:

$$w_i = \frac{S_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n S_i}, \quad (1)$$

where S_i was the sum of pairwise comparisons for the i -th criterion; n was the number of criteria.

2. Enterprise evaluation based on selected criteria

After determining the significance of each criterion, each enterprise was evaluated on a scale from 1 to 9, where 1 represented the lowest level of development for a given criterion and 9 represented the highest. The evaluations for each enterprise and criterion were normalized using the following equation:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{R_{ij} - R_{\min}}{R_{\max} - R_{\min}}, \quad (2)$$

where P_{ij} was the normalized score for the i -th enterprise on the j -th criterion;

R_{ij} was the actual score for the i -th enterprise on the j -th criterion; R_{\min} was the minimum score for the j -th criterion across all enterprises; R_{\max} was the maximum score for the j -th criterion across all enterprises.

3. Calculation of the intellectual potential index. The overall intellectual potential index (IP_i) for an enterprise was calculated as the weighted sum of normalized scores across all criteria:

$$IP_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \cdot P_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

where IP_i was the final IP_i for i -th enterprise; w_j was the weight coefficient for the j -th criterion; P_{ij} was the normalized score for the i -th enterprise on the j -th criterion.

This index enables a comparative analysis of enterprises' intellectual potential and identifies the impact of corporate social policy on the development of their intellectual resources. By applying multi-criteria evaluation methods, including AHP and the calculation of intellectual potential indices, it is possible to quantitatively assess the role of corporate social policy in shaping an enterprise's intellectual capital. This approach facilitates a systematic analysis of how various factors influence innovation potential and enhances understanding of the mechanisms through which social policy affects an organization's competitiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

R. MacGregor Pelikánová notes that the term "corporate social responsibility" (CSR) has become highly popular and is understood as a contemporary designation of a universal and widely adopted self-regulating business model that enables organizations to maintain social accountability towards themselves, their stakeholders, and society at large [18].

A. E. Raposo Junior examined scholarly articles linking marketing and CSR. The analysis reveals a shift in research focus from financial performance metrics to consumer behavior and stakeholder relations [19].

C. T. Mukaro et al. assert that intellectual capital undoubtedly serves as a critical factor in enhancing organizational efficiency. Companies require qualified professionals possessing knowledge, skills, experience, and innovative thinking to ensure business success. Their study investigates the relationship between intellectual capital and organizational performance across various business sectors in Turkey [20].

N. Chandra et al. measure intellectual capital efficiency through implementation of a non-parametric composite index method. This approach surpasses traditional intellectual capital assessment methodologies by enabling customized weighting of internal company metrics and providing precise evaluation of overall efficiency [21].

M. Kasradze et al. observe that energy sector companies actively implement CSR practices to address increasing regulatory pressures while expanding environmental impact management and risk mitigation capabilities, simultaneously focusing on economic growth. The authors identified eleven CSR indicators for the energy sector, categorized into four clusters: environmental, stakeholder communication and external image, financial, and organizational [22].

F. Wang et al. examine the impact of corporate environmental responsibility on green innovation performance using a comprehensive evaluation system. Their findings demonstrate that environmental protection investments play a mediating role in the mechanism through which corporate environmental responsibility influences green innovation efficiency [23].

T. Lyu and Q. Shen highlight that in the digital economy, platform-based internet companies face challenges related to ineffective risk management and insufficient attention to social responsibility. The authors explore appropriate CSR approaches for platform companies operating in diverse contexts [24].

S. W. Hung investigates effects of CSR on knowledge capital accumulation, research and development investments, and financial performance. The study reveals that CSR engagement can facilitate knowledge capital accumulation and research and development investments. While resources allocated to knowledge capital, research and development, or CSR promotion may negatively impact short-term profitability, research confirms these effects do not diminish investor optimism regarding future competitive advantages or financial performance [25].

J. Ali et al. examine the CSR impact on the value-added efficiency of intellectual capital in Indian food and agribusiness companies. Regression analysis revealed that CSR expenditures exert a positive and significant influence on value-added intellectual capital ($\beta = 0.119$, $p < 0.01$), encompassing all dimensions of firms' capital efficiency except structural capital. CSR demonstrated no significant effect on structural capital alone ($\beta = 0.044$, $p > 0.10$), implying that firms' structural capital efficiency remains independent of CSR expenditures [26].

W. Wu and L. Yu investigate how environmental CSR affects two dimensions of corporate technological innovation: process and product innovations. Their analysis of 241 Chinese companies demonstrates that environmental CSR positively influences innovation, with these relationships mediated by green entrepreneurial orientation [27].

R. O. H. AlObaid et al. explore CSR impact on corporate value in conjunction with knowledge-based resources. The researchers identified a significant inverse

relationship between CSR and corporate value metrics. The study also revealed that both intellectual capital and COVID-19 play complementary moderating roles in strengthening the inverse CSR-corporate value relationship [28].

M. C. López-Penabad et al. examine CSR integration in microfinance institutions (MFIs) in relation to sustainable development goals. The research highlights emerging investigation areas including digital technology and fintech innovations, climate change adaptation, while identifying critical research gaps in internationalization, corporate governance, gender diversity, and alternative financing mechanisms [29].

H. Sun and H. Xu analyze the connection between CSR and data visualization in 10-K reports filed by U.S. public companies (2004-2016). Their findings indicate CSR performance positively correlates with quantitative data visualization usage, providing insights into how companies employ data visualization techniques, particularly quantitative infographics, to communicate CSR initiatives [30].

M. H. Shoukat et al. investigate how corporate sustainability and responsibility index (CSRI) affects sustainability performance (SP) in the tobacco industry through the lens of resource-based view theory. The study established that Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) mediates the CSRI-SP relationship [31].

E. B. Mutuc and S. Cabrilo examine intellectual capital's moderating effect on CSR-financial performance relationships. Their findings indicate that while CSR and knowledge-based resources (intellectual capital) jointly enhance financial performance, developed countries show negative CSR-performance correlations without intellectual capital's moderating effect. Conversely, in developing countries, CSR improves corporate performance, with all three CSR aspects positively influencing financial metrics [32].

J. Tyan et al. study the transferability of CSR initiatives to corporate performance for achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The research concludes that organizational structure mediates the relationship between CSR strategy and corporate performance, including SDG disclosure, sales revenue, net profit, and return on equity [33].

The literature review reveals substantial scholarly attention to various aspects of CSR and intellectual capital. CSR has emerged as a prominent business model fostering organizational accountability to society and stakeholders.

Numerous studies demonstrate CSR influence across diverse business and economic dimensions [34-40], confirming that CSR participation facilitates knowledge capital

accumulation, research and development investments, and positively impacts innovations, particularly environmental and technological. Collectively, research substantiates CSR critical role in enhancing innovation, financial performance, and corporate sustainability across different countries and sectors [41-50].

RESULTS

The study evaluated the impact of corporate social policy on the intellectual potential formation of ten enterprises operating in various industries. A multi-criteria assessment method using AHP was employed, enabling the consideration of various corporate social policy factors affecting the development of organizations' intellectual resources.

1. At the first research stage, a pairwise comparison procedure was conducted to determine weight coefficients for five criteria characterizing enterprises' intellectual potential. The pairwise comparison results yielded weight coefficients for each criterion, reflecting their degree of influence on overall intellectual potential. The obtained weight values for each criterion are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Weight coefficients for intellectual potential criteria

Criterion	Weight coefficient, w_i
Employee qualification level	0.279
Access to employee training and development	0.220
Degree of innovative technology implementation	0.181
Number of scientific developments and patents	0.160
Effectiveness of social support	0.160

The weight coefficients for intellectual potential criteria were calculated using the pairwise comparison method, which forms the basis of AHP. During pairwise comparisons, experts assessed the relative importance of each of the five criteria, considering their impact on overall intellectual potential. For each criterion pair, the degree of one criterion's importance over another was determined using a 1-9 scale, where 1 indicates equal importance and 9 indicates much greater importance. Subsequently, to obtain weight coefficients, the sums of pairwise comparisons were calculated for each criterion, and corresponding coefficients were derived from these values. The calculated weight coefficients were normalized so that their sum

equals 1. The results reflect the relative significance of each criterion in intellectual potential assessment.

2. In the second research stage, after determining weight coefficients for intellectual potential criteria, enterprises were evaluated against each selected criterion. In order to standardize and ensure data comparability, all enterprise assessments by criteria were normalized using the following equation:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{R_{ij} - R_{\min}}{R_{\max} - R_{\min}} \times 100, \quad (4)$$

where P_{ij} was the normalized score for the i -th enterprise on the j -th criterion; R_{ij} was the actual score for the i -th enterprise on the j -th criterion; R_{\min} and R_{\max} were the minimum and maximum scores for the respective criterion across all enterprises.

Applying this equation to actual data yielded normalized assessment values for eight machine-building enterprises across all criteria. The normalization results are presented in Table 2, with all values ranging from 0 to 100.

Table 2

Normalized enterprise assessments by selected criteria

Enterprise	Employee qualification level (P1)	Training access (P2)	Innovation implementation (P3)	Scientific developments and patents (P4)	Social support (P5)
M1	78	65	70	62	59
Sq.m	62	74	65	58	63
M3	80	68	82	75	70
M4	73	59	68	64	55
M5	69	67	69	70	68
M6	76	63	71	72	61
M7	72	60	64	60	57

The normalization process converted all scores to a uniform scale (0-100), enabling accurate cross-enterprise comparisons while accounting for variations in intellectual potential development. This transformation assigned 100 to the best performance and 0 to the weakest within each criterion, ensuring objective subsequent calculations.

3. The third research stage involved calculating a comprehensive IP_i for each enterprise, enabling an integrated assessment of how all selected criteria collectively influence overall intellectual potential levels. The weighted aggregates

of normalized scores were computed for each organization, incorporating the established weighting coefficients.

The final IP_i index for individual enterprises was determined using the following equation:

$$IP_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \cdot P_{ij}, \quad (5)$$

where w_j was the weight coefficient for the j -th criterion; P_{ij} was the normalized score for the i -th enterprise on the j -th criterion.

Table 3

Intellectual potential indices by enterprise

Enterprise	Final IPI
M1	68.092
Sq.m	64.903
M3	75.342
M4	64.667
M5	68.560
M6	69.195
M7	63.592

It should be emphasized that the calculated composite intellectual potential indices enable a comparative analysis of the development level of enterprises' intellectual resources. These indices reflect the degree of influence exerted by corporate social policy and key factors, including staff qualifications, access to training, and implementation of innovative technologies, on organizations' overall intellectual potential. In this context, higher index values indicate more effective utilization of social policy for intellectual capital formation.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The analysis of the obtained data revealed that enterprises with high intellectual potential index values, such as M3 (75.342) and M6 (69.195), demonstrate a comprehensive approach to corporate social policy. This policy focuses on optimizing employee qualification systems, implementing innovative technologies, and developing social infrastructure, which directly contributes to the growth of organizational intellectual resources. Such an approach strengthens workforce

potential and stimulates the adoption of new innovations and technologies, fostering intellectual capital development and enhancing competitiveness.

Conversely, enterprises with lower index values, such as M7 (63.592), M2 (64.903), and M4 (64.667), show less emphasis on aspects related to intellectual asset development. This negatively impacts their innovation activity and the efficiency of human capital utilization. These organizations demonstrate limited efforts in adopting innovative technologies and improving employee qualifications. Furthermore, the lack of strategic integration between CSR and intellectual resource management constrains their potential for long-term growth and competitive advantage.

Meanwhile, enterprises with moderately high index values, such as M1 (68.092) and M5 (68.560), indicate more proactive and targeted social policy implementation. These organizations actively adopt innovations, support employee qualification programs, and develop intellectual assets, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and business resilience. In such companies, corporate social policy is integrated into intellectual resource management processes, accelerating the development of innovation potential.

Thus, the results confirm the hypothesis that corporate social policy is a critical factor in shaping and developing enterprises' intellectual capital. Companies actively implementing CSR programs demonstrate superior outcomes in employee qualification, technological innovation, and overall organizational efficiency. Conversely, enterprises with underdeveloped CSR strategies face limitations in improving competitiveness and achieving sustainable growth amid globalization and economic uncertainty.

Based on the analysis, several key conclusions can be distinguished. Firstly, corporate social policy improves employees' quality of life and acts as a catalyst for intellectual capital growth. Secondly, successful companies leverage social technologies to enhance employee potential and drive innovative solutions. Third, the absence of a holistic CSR approach and its integration with intellectual resource management may hinder long-term growth and resilience in the face of modern economic challenges. In order to enhance competitiveness and innovation potential, enterprises should more actively integrate CSR into strategic processes. This will enable more effective utilization of intellectual resources while creating conditions for sustainable development and innovation in a globally competitive environment.

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